

Review

A short overview of recycling and treatment of spent LiFePO₄ battery

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Abstract: Development in the field of electric vehicles brought great interest in recycling the spent Li-ion batteries. In particular, the value of LiFePO₄ (LFP)-type batteries have enhanced in energy market owing to its longer life span, improved discharge and charge efficiency, and safe handling. The rising utilization of such batteries has enhanced concern about their proper disposal, where improper handling could consequence in toxic material entering the environment. Consequently, waste LFP battery recycling is receiving a lot of attention. So far, two common methods have been acknowledged for battery recycling: 1) Hydrometallurgy; 2) Pyrometallurgy. The high temperature utilization in Pyrometallurgy process, limited their further application. On the other hand, hydrometallurgy process is known as promising method for precious metal digestion and regeneration. Herein, we have provided an overview about LiFePO₄ battery recycling. The recycling of cathode from its deactivation to metal recovery were sectioned. The current review article reports the problems related to the recycling process of batteries, the need to extract the metal, and possible routes for recycling. State of the art in preprocessing End-of-Life LiFePO₄ batteries and the final batteries recovery is discussed. In last, the regeneration of spent battery via different approach were discussed shortly. It is believed the proposed review would be helpful to understand the overall waste battery recycling approach.

Keywords: Spent battery; LFP cathode, recycling, Li-ion battery, regeneration

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Introduction

In order to get rid of fossil fuel related toxic off gassing, energy storage devices (ESD) are getting high attention to minimize the use of fossil fuels. Recently EVs are considering an excellent alternate for controlling the high consumption of oil resources owing to its environmentally friendly behavior, and it is believed that in coming 10-30 years, the most of the revenue of a country would be occupied by EV (electric vehicle) industries, particularly in China. Among different type of ESD devices, Lithium-ion batteries have received a high concerned due the high energy storage potential, and environmental friendless. The lithium-ion battery is a famous rechargeable battery, frequently abbreviated as Li-ion battery or LIB. The LIBs technology was developed in 1970-1980 by Richard Vazami, Akira Yoshino, and John

Goodenough, and later commercialized by Asahi Kasei and Sony in 1991. As shown in **Figure 1**, the use of LIBs is speeded in wide range, particularly in electric vehicles (EVs) industries. LIBs are widely accepted as the best energy sources for electric vehicles (EVs), portable electronic devices, and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) based on their high voltage and energy densities. Thus, the overwilling amount of daily manufacturing LIBs leads to high demand and a tremendous amount of waste batteries, eventually becoming a source of environmental concern. In addition, the growing production of LIBs has also been associated with the exhaustion of natural metal resources, particularly Lithium resources. Therefore, to fulfill the battery demand and save the environment, battery recycling and developing the next-generation sustainable solid-state lithium-ion batteries, including cathode, anode, electrolyte, are the need of time. Li-ion batteries became a secondary source of people's lives in this developed world.. China is becoming the first car sales yearly, making a 4.7% increase in the car sales business. Still, oil consumption and excessive need for foreign oil lead to limited environmental and societal sources [1, 2]. Therefore, there is a need to move toward power batteries, which are specially designed with less toxic metal and yield an excellent productive field.

In a recent report, the economic cost procuring a battery type vehicle in 2020 will be more than 100% billion US dollars. While, in the year between 2015 to 2020, the sales of EV for China are increase to 10%, which is comparatively considered more than the United States. It is predicted that in the next 10-30 years, EV industries will account for the majority of a country's income[3, 4]. In this regards, different countries have advertised many strategies to encourage electric vehicles (EVs).

This comparable upsurging of the electric vehicle market discard with expired LIBs, which is considered a big issue in upcoming environmental pollution, which would eventually contribute to secondary health issues. Besides, the increasing demand results in depletion of precious metal resources that used as active material for cathode electrode preparation, notably Li, which dramatically increases the demand of overall lithium-related minerals (as shown in Figure 1b). Therefore, the recycling of battery and its reuse are focused much to ensure the viability of future market.

There are four varieties of Li-ion batteries based on cathode material, namely, LiMn_2O_4 series, LiCoO_2 series, $\text{Li}(\text{NiCoMn})\text{O}_2$ series (NCM), $\text{Li}(\text{NiCoAl})\text{O}_2$ series (NCA), and LiFePO_4 series [5-8]. Manufacturing companies choose mainly LiFePO_4 among different cathodes as it gives stability and safety. The resources of other metals like cobalt are limited in China, so most of the metal needs to be imported, which ultimately allowed companies toward alternative sources. In LFP cathode material, cathode proved as longer life, higher safety, low cost, reduced environmental pollution, and China enriched with its raw material, results is the production and development of Li-ion batteries. Li-ion battery is commonly known as eco-friendly because of the presence of nontoxic metals. However, its composition includes some toxic electrolytes, organic chemicals, and plastics, which can lead to serious safety and environmental problems if not correctly disposed of [9, 10]. Li-ion batteries' capability is incomparable with small traditional batteries; they end their useful life in electric vehicles when their adequate capacity drops to 80% of the original total. The reuse of Li-ion batteries is not only for waste treatment but spent sources are profitable as they provide an enormous amount of Li-ion metal. The economic growth rate grows to increase by utilizing the spent sources of LiFePO_4 . With this matter of fact, here in, recycling methods of spent Li-ion LFP batteries are discussed. As Li-ion batteries are developing to increase, spent sources are the main attraction of demand.

In this review, we have provided the current status of waste batteries and its exponential growth in recent electric market. Furthermore, the review has been divided with different section of how battery recycle and reuse with the description of experimental setup and proposed process through different leaching agent are explained. In last, the future prospectus according to best of our knowledge has been provided.

Fig. 1: (a) Utilization of Lithium-ion batteries in different energy sector; (b) demand of Li from the year of 2014 to 2018.

Environmental benefits of spent LiFePO_4 batteries

LFP cathode pack contains 80% of their performance, even useable for secondary applications. However, if attention could be paid to the recovery of the useable material, there would be a big benefit of alternate material sources. It would grow the utilization of used material rather than extraction from an ore and cause environmental pollution [11]. To apply the precautionary measurement, it is estimated that the average ecological benefits of spent LiFePO_4 battery recycling amount to 2376 CNY per ton according to the China environmental, economic accounting research report [12, 13]. Following the same strategy, the environmental benefits of spent LiFePO_4 battery recycling will reach 2,342 million CNY in 2025, which is helpful for the sustainable development of resource consumption and environment protection from a social perspective greatly help in the development of a low carbon economy.

Recycling processes

Battery (LFP) mainly consists of an anode, cathode, electrolyte, separator, and other components, as displayed in **Figure 2**. Anode composition consists of different materials, same as for cathode material composition such as active material, Al, electric conductor, PVDF binder, and additives [14].

Fig. 2: Battery cell composition

The working of the battery is well known and understood. The stability and sustainability defined the best features of the cathode, which impart significant battery development, drawing interest for researchers to design processes to repair or recycle cathode in spent LFP [15, 16]. The recycling process is considered more complicated due to having a wide variety of materials and careful separation in each step [17]. Therefore, the first step pretreatment method (discharging, electrolyte treatment, crushing) and physical and chemical separation steps [18] are involved and still under the stage of the experiment. The pretreatment process involves two methods, but the most reliable and efficient dismantling process is to recycle the material. The advantage of this method is the metal casing, and plastic can be automatically separated. For manual use, careful attention should be paid, and even some researchers illustrated the manual process method [19]. After some initial step (removing plastic casing), it was immersed into liquid nitrogen and sawn in a lathe, which eventually led to the separation of the component.

Separation of active materials

After the pretreatment process, it follows the chemical/physical separation method, including thermal treatment, alkaline leaching, or organic solvent to separate the active materials [20-22]. Thermal processes differentiate materials according to their melting points [23]. However, the chemical process consists of dissolving aluminum foil in an alkali solution. The desired product LiFePO_4 is collected after filtration. Recycling of the material can be devised and divided into several methods under the following heading:

1. Recovery of valuable metals from spent LiFePO_4 batteries
2. Regeneration and utilization of LiFePO_4 from spent LiFePO_4 batteries
3. Preparation of lithium ferrite from spent LiFePO_4 batteries

Structure of LFP material

In orthorhombic olivine structure of LiFePO_4 compound, Li and Fe occupy octahedral sites while P occupies tetrahedral sites. As shown in Figure 3, in crystal lattice of LFP, the layer of FeO_6 shares octahedral corner place, and LiO_6 is linked at octahedral edge place having parallel direction toward b-axis in the form of straight-chain and along with this a three-dimensional stable structure also form through the linkage of PO_4 bridge. During Li-ion extraction, the olivine structure of FePO_4 does not change and remain at hetero-site. Moreover, the main shortage behind its excellent theoretical capacity ($\sim 170\text{mAh g}^{-1}$) is the low diffusion rate of Li-ion as well as its low intrinsic electric conductivity [24].

Fig. 3: Crystalline structure of LiFePO_4 material

Recycling strategies of spent LiFePO_4 batteries

As earlier mentioned, two recycling strategy is commonly applied for waste battery recycling: Pyrometallurgy process, where high-temperature based treatment of spent LIBs, is carried out for physical decomposition of LIBs. In this process, the molar ratio is initially adjusted, followed by a higher temperature to recrystallize and regenerate the spent LIBs material. In the second case, the hydrometallurgical process is used to individually extract metals such as Li, Co, Mn, Ni, and Fe from used LIBs. Moreover, the spent LIBs are digested by a suitable solvent such as acid, alkaline, or natural organic acid, followed by metals recovery from the leached solution via precipitation or electrochemical separation method [19]. Afterward, the metals are mixed through the hydrothermal or co-precipitation method followed by a high heat treatment process to regenerate a new cathode material.

Pyrometallurgy

The pyrometallurgical process is known as physical operation, at which high-temperature treatment of spent LIBs is carried out for physical decomposition of components of LIBs. This process mainly depends on two steps, in the first step, for the prevention of gas explosion from the electrolyte, low temperature is provided. While in the second step, a higher temperature is provided for the recrystallization of spent Lib's material. There are mainly four categories of pyrometallurgy process: smelting, calcining, roasting and refining.

Hydrometallurgical routes

Another common recycling approach is the recovery of individual metals by different leaching agent as follow:

Acid leaching

Wu et al.[25] reported HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 based leaching process for the recovery of Li and Fe from spent LFP cathode powder. In their study, they recovered Li and Fe by two-step. In the first step, spent LFP cathode powder was leached by HNO_3 , where Li was recovered as Li_2CO_3 from the filtrate by Na_2CO_3 . In the second step, in order to obtained Fe from leaching residue, leaching residue was again leached out with H_2SO_4 , where Fe was recovered as $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ by $\text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixed with NaOH through adjusting pH, respectively. In order to avoid two-step acid leaching, Wu et al.[25] also described an H_2SO_4 based leaching process for the recovery of Li and Fe from spent LFP cathode powder. In this route, H_2SO_4 acid was directly used to digest LFP completely, and then Fe and Li were recovered from filtrate as Fe

(OH)₃ and Li₂CO₃ by NH₃·H₂O+NaOH and Na₂CO₃ through adjusting pH, respectively. The proposed process by Wu et al. was displayed in **Figure 4** [25].

Fig. 4: Acid leaching process studied by Wu et al. [25]

Alkaline leaching

Wang et al.[26] studied the alkaline based leaching method for high recovery of Li, Fe, Al and Cu from spent LFP cathode material. This method includes three main procedures: “Thermal pretreatment → acid leaching → alkaline leaching → precipitation.” Firstly, in the thermal pretreatment process, spent LFP cathode powder was heated at 600 °C for four h, and then Al, Fe, Cu were separated by H₂SO₄ based acid leaching. Secondly, the alkaline based leaching was applied on leaching residue to recover Li as LiPO₄ by chemical precipitation method. The whole process proposed by Wang et al. is displayed in **Figure 5** [26].

Fig. 5: Alkaline leaching process described by Wang et al. [26]

Selective leaching of lithium from LFP-cathode material

To recover the waste LFP powder, compared with the other leaching methods as mentioned above, the selective leaching of Li and one-step separation of Fe are economical. Previously, to get individual recovery of Li and Fe, an excessive amount of strong acid was applied for completely destroying the olivine-structured LiFePO_4 cathode material. But, in the selective recovery process, selective recycling of Li and in-situ preparation of FePO_4 are achieved, in which LiFePO_4 releases Li^+ ion and turns into FePO_4 without destruction for the crystal structure, which results in less consumption of strong acid in comparison to other methods. In the selective recovery of Li, by properly control the oxidative state and proton activity of the leaching solution, Li can be selectively leached with a high extraction rate. Therefore, sometimes oxidizing agents also used for enhancing the oxidative delithiation from LFP cathode material. Along with that, the use of a smaller number of leaching agents certainly reduces the production of secondary waste, which makes this process more attractive in comparison to other recovery routes. As we know, during the selective recovery process, the recovered products are Li and FePO_4 , and that can be recycled again as a fresh precursor for

developing the new cathode material, due to that reason this process also consider as a closed-loop recycling route for used LiFePO_4 batteries. Therefore, many researchers are paying much attention to this process. For example, Li et al. investigated a low concentration H_2SO_4 -based leaching method for the selective recovery of lithium from spent LFP cathode [27], where they used 0.3 M sulfuric acid with H_2O_2 to achieve a Li-leaching rate of 96.85 % almost without Fe-leaching. Finally, lithium was recovered as Li_3PO_4 from leachate. Furthermore, Zhang et al. reported a novel process for the selective recovery of Li from waste LFP cathode material [28]. In their process, they recovered 99 % of Li selectively through oxidation leaching with sodium persulfate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$). Also, Yang et al.[29] reported a selective recovery of Li from spent LFP cathode, where they used 0.8 mol/L⁻¹ acetic acid with 6 vol.% of H_2O_2 as leaching agents at 50°C to get a 94.54 % of Li-leaching rate and a less than 1 % of Fe-leaching rate. The process flow diagram of Yang at el.[29] is displayed in **Figure 6**.

Fig. 6: Selective recovery process studied by Yang et al. [29]

Facial and green recovery is always considered as superior research when it comes to metal separation unit. Biorecovery is considered as a promising approach to recycle metal because of low cost, naturally abundant and benignity, in which complex natural organic acid are mainly responsible to dissolve the metal ion. At the moment, the natural product, such as *Phytolacca Americana* branch (PA) and tea waste (TW), bacteria (*Acid thiobacillus ferrooxidans*) (Niu et al., 2014), and fungi (*Aspergillus Niger*) (Horeh et al., 2016), have been reported for recycling spent LIBs. Very recently, Kumar et al. reported a green and facial selective recovery of Li and FePO_4 by natural organic acid from waste LFP cathode scrap. In their study, lemon juice as a natural organic acid revealed high selective recovery rate of Li. Lemon juice (LJ), a kind of organic fruit chemically known as citrus fruit due to highly rich in Citric acid. A scheme in **Figure 7a** was used to

describe the mechanism of process. They observed that the naturally presence of weak acid in LJ, Li is released into solution as the form of Li_3Cit , accompanied by Fe^{2+} in LiFePO_4 is oxidized to be Fe^{3+} as the product of FePO_4 remaining in the leaching residue. This process could be an in-situ reaction, where the olivine structure of LiFePO_4 has been directly transformed to be the olivine structure of FePO_4 . Further, in their study, pH played a vital role to extract Li and FePO_4 selectively. As shown in E-pH diagram (Figure 7b), the phase of Li was remained in solution at pH range 2-4, which is consist by using lemon juice. The leaching rate of Li in solution were reached 94.3% with minor loss of Fe (3.84%) at pH 3.

Fig. 7: (a) Mechanism of lemon juice-based bio-recycling of LFP cathode and (b) LFP pH phase state (Kumar et al., 2020)

Regeneration and utilization of LiFePO_4 from spent LiFePO_4 batteries

Solid-phase sintering method. This method, specially used for regeneration of LFP from spent LFP by solid phase sintering method divided into dismantling, cutting, separation, thermal treatment and resynthesizing [30]. The overall process involves treating the cathode plate with multiple steps and adjusting every metal ratio by adding $\text{FeC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Li_2CO_3 , and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$. Ethanol addition was to obtain the precursor, which is calcined for 24h, to get olivine LiFePO_4 . Upon consideration of results, it was provided that the LiFePO_4 powders re-synthesized under optimal conditions were near-spherical particles of $10\mu\text{m}$ with an olivine structure. The analytical study showed that LiFePO_4 with 5% carbon has the best rate of performance and cycling stability, with a discharge capacity of 148.0 mAh g^{-1} at a rate of 0.1C. This method gave the main direction for research into the spent LFP recycling method.

Solvothermal method. This method is known as the repair process developed by Zhi et al. [31]. To discharge, separation of cathode material, and reuse of recovered compound to prepare LFP cathode materials. The LFP batteries are discharged, anode and cathode are separated, aluminum foil is brought into contact with NaOH solution, separating the cathode material from its surface. The dissolution of the PVDF membrane recovered the cathode material into 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP). After LiOH solution introduced into high-pressure reactor, calcination, successive steps

regenerated material obtained with discharge capacity of 130 mAhg^{-1} and a discharge capacity retention of 99.56% after 100 cycles. Although having some steps difficult controlling, but serve as an efficient route for recycling spent LiFePO_4 batteries.

Electrochemical method. Yang et al. [32] developed electrochemical process for the repairing of cathode material from spent LiFePO_4 . This process was mainly designed into four steps: First, the discharged Li-ion batteries were dismantled by machine, after then cathode plates were soaked into dimethyl-carbonate and NMP to remove electrolyte and binder. Secondly, washing of the plate was done by ethanol to get the repaired LiFePO_4/C powder. Thirdly, the regenerated cathode is obtained by the mass ratio of carbon black and PVDF binder with LiFePO_4/C powder. In the fourth part, a half-cell was prepared by using a lithium metal sheet as an anode. The regeneration of cathode material tested and results showed the performance of lithium metal cathode by a discharge capacity of 150, 141, 131, 111, 79 and 50 mAhg^{-1} at 0.1, 0.5, 1, 5, 10 and 15C, respectively. On the evaluation of LiFePO_4/C cathode discharge capacity, regenerated cathode delivered the initial discharge capacity of 133 mAhg^{-1} at 0.1C, which is greater than the 114 mAhg^{-1} discharge capacity of the non-regenerated cathode.

Vacuum treatment method. The recovery of the positive plate can be studied through vacuum treatment. Separation of the positive plate, cleaning, drying the positive late brought into new lithium iron phosphate battery with a new negative plate. Additionally, the copper foil was obtained by burning off the carbon and binder from the harmful materials. The recovery of the copper plate was obtained by burning off the carbon and binder, and the waste plastic was directly recycled from the separator. This process generates the new positive material, ensuring the simple and recycling of several parts of spent LiFePO_4 without applying any physical/ chemical process.

Carbon-thermal reduction (CTR). CTR process is firstly carried to the regeneration of LFP cathode electrode materials. In this method, LFP waste material undergoes to leaching of metal scraps by solvent and subsequently heated at high temperature to obtain the fresh precursor. After that, a stoichiometric ratio of Li and carbon are added and regrated by CTR method under in N_2 or Ar atmosphere.

Prospectus

Indeed, the recycling process has significantly promoted the recycling of spent cathode material. Prior to the utilization of these recycling method, there are some future desires that could be adopted to encourage the recycling of spent batteries as follow: in the coming generation, technologies related to power battery re-uses will become the main research focus, and much research still needs to be carried out. Government imposing and promoting the power battery recycling techniques but some unawareness and poorly contribution toward this business brought slow improvement and limited economic growth. The related companies should formulate standards to drag the investor's interest for the recycling of the batteries. Furthermore, the utilization of end-to-life should be enlarged to enhance the overall economy of process, as well as, green method that could be viable to secondary free to environment must be encouraged. In addition, the bio based solvent are recently known as green and sustainable material, which could be applied for leaching of LFP based material owing to their leaching behavior, such type of research could be promoted to get a sustainable recycling process.

Conclusion

Development in the field of electric vehicles brought great interest in recycling the spent Li-ion batteries. In this review, we have provided the current status of waste batteries and its exponential growth in recent electric market. Furthermore, the review has been divided with different section of how battery recycle and reuse with the description of experimental setup and proposed process through different leaching agent are explained. Particularly, we have provided an overview about LiFePO_4 type battery recycling. The current review article especially reports the problems related to the recycling

process of batteries, the need to extract the metal, and possible routes for recycling. State of the art in preprocessing End-of-Life LiFePO₄ batteries and the final batteries recovery is discussed. To the end, a prospectus of current battery recycling issues has been given. We believe this review could be helpful for analysis of current battery recycling and reuse strategies.

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